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**Lutrinae Bonaparte, 1838 (Carnivora, Mustelidae)
from the Plio-Pleistocene of the Lower Omo Valley,
southwestern Ethiopia: systematics and new insights into the
paleoecology and paleobiogeography of the Turkana otters**

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ABSTRACT

On page 697, in Figure 6A, the Y axis corresponds to $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ and not to $\delta^{13}\text{C}$. Figure 6 is reproduced here.

À la page 697, dans la Figure 6A, l'axe Y correspond au $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ et non au $\delta^{13}\text{C}$. La Figure 6 est reproduite ici.

FIG. 6. — **A, B**, Stable oxygen (**A**) and carbon (**B**) isotope values for Omo carnivorans (*Enhyriodon* Falconer, 1868, felids, hyaenids) and herbivore families (Hippopotamidae; Bovidae, by tribe; Cercopithecidae, genus *Theropithecus* I.Geoffroy Saint-Hilaire, 1843; Deinotheriidae, Elephantidae, Equidae, Giraffidae, Rhinocerotidae; Suidae, by genera) from the Usno Formation and the members B and C of the Shungura Formation. Carnivoran data are from this study and herbivore data are from Souron et al. (2012), Bibi et al. (2013) and Negash et al. (2015, 2020) (see Appendix 1 for isotope values). **Bold horizontal lines** in the box and **whisker plots** represent median values, **boxes** represent first and third quartiles, and **whiskers** encompass 1.5x the interquartile range. The $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ isotope value expected for *Enhyriodon* if its diet was based exclusively on the consumption of giant oysters (*Etheria elliptica* Lamarck, 1807) is indicated in **red**. The **red box** underlines the comparisons between otters, terrestrial carnivorans (felids and hyaenids) and hippopotamids (see Stable isotope analysis results and General discussion for details).